

STATE OF METROLOGICAL SUPPORT FOR VISCOSITY MEASUREMENT

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Relevance: Today, viscosity measuring instruments are widely used in the oil industry, fuel industry, medicine, cosmetology, and other important industries for assessing product quality and safety indicators and controlling technological processes in production conditions. According to the analysis conducted, today there is a real need for metrological verification of more than 16,000 working viscometers at industrial enterprises. One of the urgent tasks is the organization of metrological verification (verification, calibration, certification) of working measuring viscometers used in the above sectors of the economy.

Purpose of the topic: Creation of conditions for improving the quality and competitiveness of domestic products through the development and improvement of the calibration system of measuring instruments, consideration of issues of developing mechanisms for effective interaction in metrology with international and regional metrological organizations.

Methods and techniques of the topic: In order to promote the integration of the Republic of Uzbekistan into the international economy and international systems for ensuring the uniformity of measurements as an equal partner, the international standard ISO/IEC 17034:2025 "Requirements for the Competence of Testing and Calibration Laboratories," a number of analytical methods, instrumental methods for obtaining accurate results using optical and physicochemical measuring instruments, and experimental methods for analyzing results were used.

Result: International comparisons play a significant role in ensuring metrological traceability. Standard samples (SS) are used at all stages of the measurement process, including verification, calibration, and accuracy control of measurement procedures (methods). However, today such solutions are imported at the expense of foreign currency.

Today, in the metrological support of viscometers, the SVM 3000 Shtabinger type viscometer is increasingly used as a high-quality measuring instrument for measuring the kinematic viscosity, dynamic viscosity, density, and temperature of liquid media. The viscometer consists of a structure, combined in one housing, consisting of a cell for measuring the viscosity of a liquid, an electronic thermostat, a unit for processing measurement data, a liquid crystal display, and control keys.

Simultaneously and under certain conditions, as a result of measuring the viscosity and density of liquid media, it is possible to automatically convert dynamic viscosity to kinematic viscosity. This device has a standard mode for calculating the viscosity index in accordance with the ASTM D 2270 "Practice for Calculating Viscosity Index From Kinematic Viscosity at 40° and 100°C" standard.

This device is capable of measuring dynamic viscosity 0.2 - 20000 mPa•s, kinematic viscosity 0.2 - 20000 mm²/s, density up to 650 - 2000 kg/m³, temperature from -40 °C to +100 °C.

Uzbekistan is a member of the regional metrological organization COOMET ("Euro-Asian Cooperation of National Metrological Institutions"). Today, the "Physicochemical, Optical-Physical, and Temperature Quantities" section is a structural subdivision of the State Institution "UzNMI." The section uses measurements for various values and quantities, ensuring their metrological traceability with respect to the international system of units.

Conclusions: Calibration of viscometers ensures the accuracy and reliability of measurement results. Calibrated viscometers play an important role in product quality control and operation in accordance with international standards.